

Like a
PRO

Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy

**LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment
Citizen Innovation Living Labs**

Funded by
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Imprint

Title

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Project Title

LIKE-A-PRO. From niche to mainstream – alternative proteins for everybody and everywhere

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	1	4. Logistics	28
1.1. The LIKE-A-PRO Project	3	4.1 Location & accessibility	28
1.2 The LIKE-A-PRO Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs	4	4.1.1 Why are location and accessibility important?	29
1.3 What is this Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy?	6	4.1.2 Guidelines for choosing the right location	30
		4.2 Timing & duration	32
2. Identifying the WHO – who are the participants?	8	5. Summary	33
2.1 Participants	8	6. References	35
2.1.1 Diversity & Inclusion	9	7. Appendices	36
2.1.2 Guidelines for fostering diversity and inclusion	10	Appendix 1: Poster	36
2.1.3 Motivations for participating	12	Appendix 2: Flyer	37
2.2 Multipliers	15	Appendix 3: Social media post	38
2.2.1 Engaging multipliers: how to get them on board?	17	Appendix 4: Recruitment email	39
2.2.2 A step-by-step approach	18		
3. Identifying the HOW – how to recruit participants?	19		
3.1 The messaging	19		
3.1.1 Developing your messages	21		
3.2 Tools	23		
3.2.1 Tips when choosing the tools	26		
3.3 Examples	27		

1.

Intro- duction

European diets are not in line with sustainability recommendations, which has led to well-known environmental, economic, and social challenges, including elevated health risks ^[1]. **European people** despite **being aware of their negative impact**, continue to **predominantly rely on animal-based products** as their **main source of protein intake** (approx. 67% of our diets are based on animal-based foods). Furthermore, 94% of Europeans still consume animal-based products on a daily basis ^[2].

The **urgency to transition** towards more **sustainable food systems**, including **sustainable food consumption patterns**, has **inspired a number of initiatives**:

1. Targeting European consumers

– directly or indirectly.

2. of various formats

– from awareness raising, information provision, education, policy efforts, to interventions in food environments including provision of new products and services.

3. driven by different actors

– public, private and everyone in-between, at various levels of operation.

In addition, **a key instrument** to make our food consumption patterns more sustainable is the **development, promotion, and integration of products from alternative protein sources in our diets** ^[3].

The **impact of such initiatives** has been **profound** with **elevated sustainability consciousness** among European consumers. **Nonetheless**, there is **little evidence showing the shift** towards more sustainable food consumption patterns **is occurring broadly, holistically, and/or quickly enough** to match the scale of the needed transformation.

This can be **attributed to a number of factors** related to complex information environments, conflicting sustainability narratives, prevailing consumerism and wasteful cultures as well market and food environment lock-ins [3]. Additionally, when it comes to alternative protein products, an array of factors contribute towards their low uptake, such as

- their novel character [4]
- lack of knowledge among consumers about their benefits [5]
- negative perception of sensory properties [4]
- needs for balanced diets, potential allergen issues [4],
- strong hold of Europeans to existing diets driven either by social and cultural norms [6],
- availability/ accessibility and affordability [7, 8],
- lack of clear information [9],
- segregated promotion and marketing of such products (i.e., differentiation from their counterparts with terminology such as vegan or vegetarian) [6, 9], as well as
- supply issues such as shortages and gluts or failures [10],

among other factors.

Therefore, it is **pivotal to further engage people actively** with the topic and **seek to find out what information European consumers have and need/ expect** when it comes to sustainable food consumption and **what is required to support, as well as empower** them to adopt **more sustainable food consumption patterns**, including the **integration of alternative proteins in their diets**. In here, especially important is to coherently **uncover and account for the dynamic relationship between personal factors** determining food choices and the **context in which they are made** (i.e., food environments) and reinforce each other for a positive change.

This is **exactly the purpose of the LIKE-A-PRO project** and **its Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs**.

1.1 The LIKE-A-PRO project

The LIKE-A-PRO project aims to **accelerate the shift** towards **and normalise healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns** by diversifying and increasing the **availability, accessibility, and uptake** of alternative sources of protein and specific products.

Sixteen new alternative protein products will be developed during the course of the project, based on ingredients from **seven protein sources** which are novel, sustainable, EU-based, healthy, affordable and industry viable. In addition to these products, LIKE-A-PRO will **co-design and promote other type of solutions**, such as governance mechanisms which hold the potential to promote alternative protein supply and products in food environments, including their promotion and uptake at the consumer level. Examples of these include policies that look at reducing the portfolio of unsustainable products, marketing strategies, guidelines for human-centric campaigns and similar.

Rapeseed

Mealworm

Krill

Microbial

Mushrooms

Fungus

Peas

Four **interlinked and iterative clusters of activities** will support reaching out the project goals:

Food environments and consumers

In this cluster, the focus is placed on better understanding the consumer behavioural determinants, their food choices, and the necessary food environment (contextual) frameworks that enable a higher uptake of alternative protein products.

Alternative protein product diversification and development

The central goal of cluster 2 activities is to diversify the alternative protein supply and develop new alternative protein products, thereby increasing the availability and accessibility of such products in the European markets. Best product value propositions will be developed based on consumer, market, and regulatory considerations.

Mobilising food system actors

The project will work with key food system actors to support them in utilising the project learnings and empower them to make alternative protein products an easy and economically viable choice via their diversified & increased market supply and favourable food environment conditions.

Impact and regulatory assessment

This cluster will ensure that the project will bring about positive changes in terms of health and sustainability of the European food system. Socio-economic, health, and environmental impact assessments as well as alignment with regulatory and ethical considerations are central to this clusters.

The food environments and consumers, and to lesser degree the development of alternative protein products, are the clusters which will interact with the consumer engagement activities through Living Labs.

1.2 The LIKE-A-PRO Food Environment Citizen Innovation Living Labs

Explore food environments

from the **perspective of European citizens and their consumption realities** (how consumers make their choices in such environments, how easy it is, what are the challenges/opportunities and similar).

Test and receive

some **feedback on the newly developed alternative protein products** also, naturally, only where possible and while complying with all regulatory and ethical requirements in a high standard manner.

Uncover and study

the most **influential consumer behavioural determinants**, the leveraging of which has the potential to drive the shift towards healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns.

Explore and promote

entry points in food environments in the form of governance mechanisms or solutions, the introduction of which can create favourable conditions in such environments to facilitate the much-needed dietary shift.

Two types or formats will comprise the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs as a means towards generating the desired results and fulfilling the goals we have set out for ourselves, namely:

1. Conventional exchanges and co-creation

with lab participants where, through a variety of methods and facilitation techniques (workshop style), the project will explore consumer behaviour and uncover the main determinants that shape our food consumption patterns, including the appetite to integrate alternative proteins in our diets. In a more simplified manner, the participants will exchange around key questions and will be encouraged to share their insights.

2. Interaction at the point of sale

where the project team will be present at different food environments such as, indicatively, supermarkets, restaurants, canteens, food markets. to explore through interviews and surveys food consumption behaviours in their more natural habitat. In such cases, the partners will engage and seek the approval of the relevant institutions so the activities can be conducted in their premises and/or in proximity.

Since in the project we are developing new products, we will aim to receive consumers feedback on those too. The feedback could be on the taste and/or the rest of the organoleptic qualities, as well as on packaging where feasible. In the product tasting scenario, consumers will be presented only with those products that are produced with EFSA approved ingredients. In any other case, the feedback will be by means of the other organoleptic qualities.

For a more detailed overview of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs, please have a look at the Living Labs' Governance Framework.

1.3 What is this Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy?

This Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy (PRES) helps local lab implementers to maximise people’s participation in the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs and supports them in their recruitment and maintenance of participants’ interest. More specifically, the PRES describes:

Who are the participants or the audience

of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs, including a deep dive into how to ensure a diverse sample.

Disclaimer: please note that all the suggestions within this PRES are not exhaustive, and often local lab implementers know strategies that are suited to their local context.

How to recruit participants

by providing a thorough explanation of people’s motivations to take part and how to tap into these motivations to aid participant recruitment, including advice on the textual and visual messaging to use and an overview of different tools that can be used for recruitment. In addition, an explanation on how to use multipliers i.e., other organisations who can spread the word and/or provide their space for engagement with people (e.g., supermarket restaurant, canteen, CSOs etc.) is provided.

A strategy for the implementation

of each living lab format, including guidelines for location and accessibility, timing and duration and examples of suitable recruitment materials.

A blueprint

on how to retain contact with participants.

This PRES is primarily meant to address the **project’s local lab implementers** in the Living Labs pilot countries. Nonetheless, its **open and flexible language** allows for it to be **read by everyone who might be interested in how to successfully recruit and engage participants** within a living lab or other form of field research, beyond the context of the LIKE-A-PRO project.

Complementing the PRES and jointly laying down the foundations of the Living Labs are:

The LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs Governance Framework

Outlines the key procedural considerations that are necessary to factor in for the successful planning, establishment, running and monitoring of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs. The governance framework defines and brings together aspects related to the labs' vision, purpose as well as specific themes of focus; the target group; place and timeline of implementation; operational procedures; and the overview of the team and people delivering the labs and their roles and responsibilities.

The LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs Manual

A guideline on organising and conducting lab meetings and interaction points with consumers. The Manual will act as a protocol for the various meetings/interaction points and will be developed in parts preceding each lab iteration and meetings/interaction points within.

Three “Train of the Trainers” (ToTs) workshops

These are implemented for the purpose of ensuring that all lab implementers are on the same level of understanding regarding the Living Labs and have the necessary skills to carry them out.

2.

Identifying the WHO are the participants?

A first step towards organising the Living Labs is identifying who the participants should be. This section gives an overview of the characteristics of (1) the people / consumers that will directly participate in the Living Labs (also called **participants**), and (2) the institutions or organisations that can help recruit these participants and / or provide the space for engagement (also called **multipliers**).

2.1 Participants

In order to obtain valuable and reliable data from the Living Labs, it is important that the participant sample reflects the characteristics of society as a whole. Two key concepts in achieving this are **diversity** and **inclusion**. These fundamental concepts emphasize the **recognition, acceptance, and celebration of differences** among individuals and communities.

2.1.1 Diversity & inclusion

The sample should include a balanced mix of people from different age groups, genders, education levels, cultural backgrounds, religions, and the like, also known as **diversity**. Moreover, the Living Labs need to provide a safe and comfortable space for all kinds of different groups and individuals to express their opinions, thoughts and ideas, also known as **inclusivity**.

Adopting research practices that are informed by principles of diversity and inclusion can contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of the data, leading to more nuanced and applicable research outcomes. It is important to reflect how different groups and individuals think and feel about the consumption of more alternative proteins, and how they respond to potential mechanisms that might be introduced to promote the consumption and integration of alternative proteins into our diets. By embracing diversity and promoting inclusion, the Living Labs can pose a rich and dynamic research environment that reflects the complexities of the real world, leading to more meaningful and impactful outcomes. In order to gain insights from groups and individuals with different perspectives, efforts should be made to include participants from a range of different:

- Age groups (16 and above)
- Genders (e.g. women, men, non-binary, other)
- Residencies (e.g. urban, peri-urban or rural areas) (please note that 15% of the LIKE-A-PRO Living Labs should come from rural areas)
- Education levels (e.g. primary, secondary, tertiary and above)
- Cultural backgrounds (e.g. people with diverse ethnicities, religions)
- Income (e.g. low, medium, high; think also of unemployed citizens, people with social benefits)
- Household composition (e.g. single person households, students, couples without children, couples with children)
- People with disabilities (e.g. mental / physical)
- Other population groups that are, or are at risk of being marginalised (e.g. migrant populations)

It is important to mention that we are not only interested in the opinions, thoughts, and ideas of the 'green consumer': recruitment efforts should be adapted in such a way that people with all different kinds of values are engaged in the Living Labs. For instance, when looking at the example of food environments, this means that we should not work exclusively with sustainable supermarkets, organic farmers markets or plant-based restaurants, but broaden the scope to include any kind of consumer.

2.1.2 Guidelines for fostering diversity and inclusion

Now that we know what diversity and inclusion entail and why they are important principles, let's look into how we can make sure the Living Labs are as diverse and inclusive as possible. Some general strategies that can be applied to all living lab types/formats are:

Inclusive communication

This goes for both your messages and the tools you use to disseminate your messages (more information on messaging and tools can be found in Chapter 3). For instance, it is advised to use inclusive language and imagery in recruitment materials to appeal to a wide audience. Moreover, it is recommended to use a combination of both online and offline tools in order to appeal to a broad target audience (e.g. some elderly might not use technological devices and otherwise miss out on your recruitment messages).

Culturally competent facilitation

Train facilitators to understand and respect diverse cultures, ensuring all participants feel heard and valued.

Small group set-up

It might be useful to divide participants into smaller breakout groups, to make sure everybody has the time and opportunity to speak and doesn't feel intimidated by a large setting (this is valid for online and offline meetings). You can also suggest participants to write down ideas on post-its (or in the "chat" function of online meetings), in case they are not all comfortable sharing out loud.

Participant support

Offer support services, such as sign language interpreters or written materials in different languages, catering to participants' specific needs.

Feedback loops

Establish feedback mechanisms where participants can express concerns or suggestions, ensuring ongoing inclusivity improvements.

Moreover, each living lab format has its own tailored strategies that can help increase diversity and inclusion:

For **conventional exchanges and co-creation with lab participants**, diversity and inclusion can be fostered by:

- **Venue selection:** Choose locations accessible to diverse communities, ensuring they feel comfortable and welcome.
- **Participant outreach:** Engage with community leaders and organizations representing various demographics to encourage diverse participation.
- **Cultural sensitivity:** Train facilitators to be culturally sensitive, ensuring interactions respect different beliefs and practices.
- **Virtual participation:** Consider offering virtual participation options for those unable to attend in person due to location constraints or other factors.

For **interaction at the point of sale**, you can think of increasing diversity and inclusion through the following guidelines:

- **Venue selection:** Opt for food environments located in diverse neighbourhoods, catering to varied income groups and cultural backgrounds. For instance, do not only visit the conventional supermarket chains, but also think of visiting a Turkish or Asian supermarket.
- **Inclusive observations:** Train researchers to observe without bias, respecting the diverse shopping and consumption behaviours and preferences of different communities.
- **Translation services:** Provide translation services if needed, so that participants who speak different languages can also fully engage.

2.1.3 Motivations for participating

One of the most important aspects when recruiting the right participants for your sample, is understanding their motivations to partake. What drives them? For what reasons might they be interested in the Living Labs? Different groups and individuals might have different motivations, leading to different ways they can be incentivized to take part in the Living Labs. In order to recruit a sample as diverse as possible, it is therefore important to understand these motivations, so that the recruitment strategy can be tailored accordingly.

To put it in other words: it is important for you to understand the various reasons **why** consumers might be interested to join the Living Labs (motivation), and **how** to tap into these reasons (incentives). An overview of these motivations and incentives is given in **Table 1** below. Most of the potential motivations for participants to take part in the Living Labs are interlinked, and participants may want to take part for more than just one of the reasons mentioned below. Therefore, it is important to base your recruitment strategy on multiple motivations. More about how to include the motivations into your messaging is explained in **Section 3.1**.

Table 1a. Overview of participant motivations and incentives (it continues in the next page).

Motivation	Potential incentives
The topic of alternative proteins is close to people's interest and values (e.g. health, environmental, sustainability and/or animal welfare)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Highlighting how the outcomes of the Living Labs will contribute to a (positive) change in, for instance, dietary health/sustainability/ animal welfare across Europe.• Highlighting that participants will be able to have a voice on the matter, including on challenges and opportunities (e.g. actively communicating that they will be truly listened to, explaining how their input will be used, enabling them to see the impact of their participation).• Emphasising how LIKE-A-PRO as a project focuses on healthier diets for all/a more animal-friendly food system and/or how it has pro-environmental character.• Inviting important stakeholders (e.g. representative from the local municipality/important businesses/CSOs/NGOs) can help participants feel like they are being listened to and that their opinions are acknowledged and taken into account.• Offering participants access to exclusive insights or early results from the research.

Keep in mind that this goes both ways: for instance, some people value sustainability and strive towards a greener future, but others might also value sustainability in the sense that they think it should not be so focused on.

Table 1b. Overview of participant motivations and incentives (it continues in the next page).

Motivation	Potential incentives
<p>Desire for change Participants may be motivated by a strong aspiration for a transformation in their dietary habits and/or be committed to influencing broader societal shifts.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing information on how the outcomes of the Living Labs might contribute to positive changes in food consumption patterns. • Providing participants with an exclusive collection of recipes featuring alternative protein sources, encouraging them to try new, nutritious meals. • In collaboration with multipliers, offering other benefits such as discounts on healthy food products / alternative protein products or educational sessions/webinars on the environmental benefits of adopting alternative protein diets. • Highlighting that participants will discuss with others about (the consumption of) alternative protein foods and help design solutions to increase alternative protein food intake, assessing the barriers and opportunities to such solutions.
<p>Curiosity and learning Participants may be motivated to take part in the Living Labs because the topic of alternative protein foods is new and exciting to them, and they are interested in discovering new things.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasising that participants will get a chance to taste (when safe and approved) and test alternative protein products. • Offering educational materials/sessions/webinars to educate people on the topic of alternative protein foods. • Offering participants access to exclusive insights or early results from the research.
<p>Product development Participants may be motivated by the idea that they are contributing to the development of new alternative protein sources.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasising the aspects of the Living Labs related to the development of new alternative protein products. • Highlighting that participants will have the chance to co-create/co-develop these new alternative protein products.

Table 1c. Overview of participant motivations and incentives.

Motivation	Potential incentives
<p>Sense of (broader) community Participants are motivated by being part of a research project across European countries.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlighting how participants can become part of a community across borders by taking part in the Living Labs (e.g. explaining that this research takes place across 11 pilot countries). To capitalise on this, think of creating/directing citizens to a common webpage or tool such as Slack, where they can exchange with participants from their own Living Labs as well as others across the pilot regions, exchanging views, ideas, and values.
<p>Economic motivations Some participants may be motivated by receiving compensation for the time they invested participating in the Living Labs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LIKE-A-PRO cannot offer financial incentives for participation in the Living Labs. However, you can think creatively about in-kind incentives you could offer to participants. For instance, you can partner with local multipliers to offer incentives (e.g. tickets to certain events, access to local sport or cultural facilities) or giveaways (e.g. a dinner at a local plant-based restaurant, a plant-based cookbook or the like).
<p>Social cohesion/networking Participants can be motivated by having a chance to interact with other people.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organising social activities after the Living Labs to help bring together the community, such as networking events, a neighbourhood walk, get together for a drink, small networking opportunity etc.

Tailoring incentives to align with participants' motivations increases engagement and ensures that the rewards resonate with their interests and preferences and this would help to overcome the self-selection and/or volunteer bias. Of course, the motivations and incentives

highlighted above are general across populations. You should always take the local context into account when thinking of how to motivate and incentivise people, as you as a lab implementer probably know best what works within your culture, context and setting.

2.2 Multipliers

In order to successfully recruit enough suitable participants for the Living Labs, it is useful to understand how to make use of the ‘snowball effect’. Snowball sampling means that we make use of a small pool of initial informants (also known as **multipliers**) to recruit, through their networks, other participants that are suitable for the Living Labs. These multipliers are individuals or organisations who can help lab implementers both to broaden and target their outreach. For instance, some multipliers (e.g. food environments) might be able to provide a location for hosting the Living Labs, and thereby help you recruit participants. So please keep in mind: identifying and making use of multipliers does not need to be a complicated or time-consuming task: in fact, it will make your life as a lab implementer much easier!

You are advised to make a list of your local contact persons or valuable local organisations/institutions that are deemed suitable in helping you reach out to and recruit citizens.

The kind of organisations/institutions that you should think of when making such a list are:

Food environments

(e.g. supermarkets, restaurants, canteens, farmers markets)

- Provide the perfect location to interact with consumers during their natural purchase/consumption behaviour; hence, they serve as a perfect multiplier for the point of sale living lab formats.
- Can disseminate recruitment materials in-store (such as posters, flyers) or online (for instance, through local social media accounts) to recruit participants.
- Provide a great location for in-person recruitment due to face-to-face interactions with broad customer base.
- Supermarkets/canteens/restaurants might provide a useful and accessible location to host Living Labs.

Municipalities / local public authorities:

- Likely have experience in reaching out to and engaging with their citizens.
- May have contacts and resources to offer, in particular if you can show how the Living Labs connect to local initiatives/objectives.

Educational institutions

(e.g. universities, schools, research institutions):

- Likely have experience in recruiting participants for similar research projects and extensive useful (local) networks.
- May be able to host some of the Living Labs.

Civil Society Organisations (CSOs):

- Relevant CSOs include those working on environmental topics (such as the European branches of the WWF, Friends of the Earth, Greenpeace, the European Environmental Bureau and its national/regional members, Climate Action Network Europe and its members), animal welfare topics or health topics. Can be on local, regional and/or national level.
- Can help recruit participants through their extensive networks (e.g. by means of newsletters, websites, or social media networks).

Personalised service sector

(e.g. hairdressers, drycleaners, beauty salons, tailors, florists etc.)

- Are often a trusted stakeholder with direct ties to the local community. Therefore, they can help with in-person recruitment as well as recruiting people through flyers/posters/social media/newsletters/website etc.

Other organisations that could help reach out to different demographic groups

- Think, for instance, of teachers' and parents' organisations, community centres, youth organisations, neighbourhood elderly centres, social housing organisations, anti-poverty organisations, language centres).

2.2.1 Engaging multipliers: how to get them on board?

Just as for recruiting individual participants, it is useful to map out multipliers' potential motivations for helping to recruit Living Labs participants. So, what's in it for them? In the following we list several potential motivations for multipliers:

Facilitating consumer needs

Multipliers might want to facilitate the needs of their customers by informing them about innovations, social/environmental projects, etc.

Meaning/change-making

Multipliers, just as citizens, want to feel that by helping and recruiting participants for the Living Labs, they are making a positive change and contributing to a greater goal (e.g. in terms of environmental sustainability, animal welfare or health).

Sustainable profiling

Multipliers might see helping with participant recruitment for the Living Labs as an interesting opportunity in terms of CSR that can help them create a more sustainable image.

Research outcomes

Multipliers might be interested in better understanding (local) consumer behaviour and motivations/barriers with regards to the consumption of alternative protein foods since this can benefit them, for instance, for marketing, sales, or research purposes. Tip: if possible, you can discuss with the multiplier what kind of information from this research would potentially be beneficial to them and incorporate a research question regarding that into your interactions. This can create a win-win situation!

Project learning

Multipliers might benefit from the project learnings, both at the consumer level, but also, for instance, at a product level. Of course, this might apply more to certain multipliers (e.g. food environments, educational institutions) than others.

2.2.2 A step-by-step approach

So, now that we have identified the potential multipliers and their motivations to help recruit participants for the Living Labs, let's look at a step-by-step approach on how to get them on board:

Tips for communicating with a potential multiplier:

Begin with a brief introductory email: introduce who you are, shortly explain the Living Lab (LL) logic and ask for an opportunity to meet to learn more about the organization, the work they do and the possibility of collaborating.

Develop a one-page summary of the LLs: using the Governance Framework, you can develop a one-pager that explains in simple terms what the Living Labs are. Once you've gotten a positive reply to your email, you can schedule a (online) meeting and attach this one-page study summary to the introductory email. This will prepare them for your first conversation about your and their potential role. It gives them time to digest the information and formulate questions for you and possibly explore interest within the organization before meeting you. Remember: always use layman's terms when talking about the LL!

Don't be afraid to use the telephone: if you've followed up on your first email and you still don't get a reply, don't be afraid to pick up the phone. Personal contact sometimes works faster and better. Don't feel bad – people just might have missed your email or haven't had time to respond.

1. Make a list

First, you should compose a list of multipliers that could be of use within your local context.

2. Set priorities

You do not have to approach all these multipliers all at once. It is useful to first define which multipliers would be most advantageous to reach out to or which connections already exist within your network. This provides a good starting point for your multiplier approach.

3. Be informed

Before approaching multipliers to work together, you should make sure to be informed about the organisation/institutions/individuals you're contacting. It is always important to know the person or organisation you are talking to. For instance, familiarize yourself with their work and interests. This will help you be aligned from the start and helps you define the 'why' in step 4.

4. Formulate the 'why'

To increase the chances of success, it is advised to think about areas of common interest and consider the benefits multipliers could experience from offering their help in recruiting participants for the Living Labs. It is important to try to clearly formulate these benefits, to make it as clear as possible to multipliers what's in it for them.

5. Use a personal approach

Based on the information you have gathered and the benefits you have formulated, it is important to make personalized messages for each multiplier you are approaching. Using such a personalized approach increases the chances of success. After all, everyone likes personal attention!

3.

Identifying the HOW to recruit participants?

After having identified the participants and their motivations, it is time to understand how to reach them. How should you approach them in such a way that they are most likely to agree to participate? This chapter will dive deeper into how to optimize your messaging both textually and visually and explain which tools can be used to reach out to potential participants.

3.1 The messaging

Communication is key in recruiting participants, and you have only one chance to make a good first impression. Therefore, crafting the right message requires careful consideration. Before starting to even write your message, it is useful to complete a creative brief that will help guide you through the essential goals and considerations for creating an effective recruitment tool. It's not merely about putting information on a flyer: the participant and motivational factors mentioned earlier are crucial here. A single word can put someone off, and specific colours and images (or the lack thereof) can either attract or discourage potential participants.

So, before you even start, it is important to answer the following questions:

1. Who is the target audience of your message?

Who do you want to reach with your communication? How do they see themselves? What are their goals?

2. What are your objectives?

What do you want your target group to think, feel or do after having seen or heard your message? The overall objectives and those of the lab iterations (as seen in the Governance Framework and the Manual) can help greatly here.

3. What are potential obstacles?

Can you think of any beliefs, cultural practices, misinformation, or anything else that can stop your target group from participating?

4. What is your key promise?

It is useful to define one promise or incentive that can outweigh the obstacle defined in step 3 in the eyes of your target group. Tip: formulate this promise in the format “If [desired behaviour], then [benefit]”. You can use the motivations and incentives in **Section 2.1.3** to formulate this promise.

5. How can you support this promise?

Here you should argue why your promise holds true.

Since the Living Labs have a broad target audience, it might be useful to answer the above mentioned questions for every different (demographic) target group you want to reach so that you can tailor your messaging accordingly.

3.1.1 Developing your messages

Once you've answered the questions above, you can start thinking of how to formulate and convey your message. When creating an attractive and engaging message that speaks to a diverse target audience, it is important to take the following factors into account:

Simplicity

The wording of messages should be short and simple, in local languages, and easy-to-understand by all, avoiding jargon and technical terms. However, this doesn't necessarily mean that messages should be too obvious – it could be a good idea to tell people something they don't already know in order to spark their curiosity.

Clarity

Messages need not only be simple, but also clear. It is important that consumers can easily understand:

- What is expected of them and how they will contribute (purpose, scope, process)?
- Why should they take part (e.g. your key promise)?
- What are the expected outcomes?
- What are the timeline and long-term perspectives?
- What are the practical details: timing, location, logistics, how to sign up?
- Lab implementers should also be able to explain the aims and ethos of LIKE-A-PRO in simple and consistent terms.

Positivity

As much as possible, your messaging should be positive, tapping into the different motivations that consumers can have and benefits they can gain from participating in the Living Labs. Threatening scenarios of a “doom and gloom” future should be avoided.

Relatability & relevance

In order for the messages to have the desired effect, consumers should be able to relate to the concepts, meaning and values to which the message speaks. You can achieve this by:

- **Tying messaging to local ongoing debates, concerns, events, and actualities.** You can do your own research into this, as well as reach out to local municipalities to get more information. For instance: the topic of alternative protein consumption can be tied to World Veganism Day, debates on the environmental footprint of our food etc.
- **Tailoring messages to different (demographic) target groups.** It is important to explain to consumers how the Living Labs can be of relevance to them. For instance, abstract and general discussions about the protein transition may not be of interest to people living in poverty whose first and foremost concern is just having something to eat on their plates every night. However, if the topic of alternative protein foods is linked to concerns about (alternative) protein prices, this can be made much more relevant. Moreover, you may wish to emphasise the welcoming and inclusive nature of the Living Labs, to help convince target groups who fear being excluded or marginalised in the discussions.

Attractiveness

An important part of the communication towards potential participants is the visual presentation of your message. The use of attractive colours, images, typography, and illustrations can strengthen your message and help convince consumers to participate. Hence, the visual design of your message deserves careful consideration.

After you've developed your messages, it is always good to take a final look at them with a critical eye, asking yourself the following questions:

- Can we make it easier?
- Can we make it feel more normal?
- Can we optimize the language?
- Can we make it more fun and relevant?
- Can we make people feel more included?
- Can we tap more into people's existing values?

Once you're happy with your messages, it might be useful to test your messaging in order to collect feedback from your different target groups. This can help you adjust your message and make sure that it resonates with your target audience as well as possible. The multipliers could help you reach the right people to test your message.

3.2 Tools

Different target groups use different media channels. Therefore, choosing the right medium is essential to reach potential Living Labs participants.

Table 2 below provides an overview of the different communication tools that can be used to recruit participants, divided into online and offline tools. You can decide on which tool to use depending on the target group you're trying to reach, your capacities and (financial) resources. Moreover, it is advised to use a mix of both messages and communication tools in order to reach a wide range of consumers.

Table 2a. Overview of different communication tools.

	Tool	Pros	Cons	Most suitable for
Offline	Flyers / posters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be left in different locations • Easy to use in well-visited spaces that target group visits (e.g. supermarkets, restaurants, public transport, schools, universities, community centres) • Can be strategically disseminated (e.g. in mailboxes of targeted areas) • Possibility to include all necessary information • Visually appealing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination can be time intensive • Often discarded after once read • May be seen as unimportant thus less effective 	Conventional exchanges & interaction at the point of sale
	Verbal communication (e.g. word of mouth, phone calls, local events, and conferences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal and more convincing • Can lead to snowballing effect • Great way to reach the less mobile and elderly target groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time intensive 	Conventional exchanges & interaction at the point of sale

Table 2b. Overview of different communication tools.

	Tool	Pros	Cons	Most suitable for
Offline	(Local) newspapers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Builds audience quickly • Short lead time for space and material • Can have large reach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Might have high out of pocket costs • Relatively inefficient • Cluttered environment • Circulations are in decline • Short shelf life • Often discarded 	Conventional exchanges
	(Local) television	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of visuals, sound, and motion • High reach • Immediate reach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Might have high out of pocket costs • High production costs • Lot of competition for audience's attention 	Conventional exchanges
	(Local) radio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient • More segmented audiences; hence, easier targeting • Lower out of pocket costs • Low production costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lot of competition for audience's attention • Not suited for getting an immediate response • More limited reach than television 	Conventional exchanges
Online	Mailing lists/ newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relatively easy • Time-efficient • Can reach already engaged audience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not suitable for all target groups • Contact details are needed (you can think, for instance, of approaching other organizations and ask to write something in their newsletter) • Keep GDPR in mind 	Conventional exchanges & interaction at the point of sale

Table 2c. Overview of different communication tools.

	Tool	Pros	Cons	Most suitable for
Online	Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be own website but also integrated into existing websites (e.g. of multipliers) • When incorporated into existing website: relatively easy and time-efficient 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not suitable for all target groups 	Conventional exchanges
	Social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to reach different target groups depending on the medium (e.g. Instagram, Facebook, X, LinkedIn) • Possibility to diversify content (e.g. informative text-based to fun video-content or quizzes) • Influencers and community-based groups can help share messages • Easy and accessible • High potential reach (especially if you have some advertising budgets to advertise to the desired target group) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not suitable for all target groups • Gradual increase in audience reach • High competition for capturing audience's attention 	Conventional exchanges & interaction at the point of sale
	Community apps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sure to reach the right target group • Cost-effective • Can be done with help of multipliers that post messages on there 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited demographic diversity • Selection bias • Not suitable for all target groups 	Conventional exchanges

3.2.1 Tips when choosing tools

Amongst the many possibilities, it can be difficult to decide which tools to use.

1. Understand your audience

Familiarize yourself with your target population's (online) habits and preferences. Monitor the websites and social media platforms they use, which can guide your communication strategy. For example, if your audience is active on Facebook, consider creating a page there. Pay attention to their content preferences, such as photos or videos, and the language they use. This information is invaluable for crafting effective messages.

2. Diversify your tool set

Recognize that not all methods are equally effective for reaching different populations. To meet your recruitment goals, it's best to use a variety of tools. Assess your target participants, identify suitable tools for different groups, and find ways to overcome specific barriers they might face. For instance, it is a good idea to combine online communication (e.g. social media, websites) with strategically placed printed materials, such as flyers and posters in community centres, libraries, markets, and bulletin boards. In case your resources allow it, direct word-of-mouth engagement with people in specific areas, especially vulnerable groups, can also be effective.

Here are some tips to consider in order to recruit a target audience as broad as possible:

3. Embrace local media

National media outlets like newspapers and television can be expensive. Instead, focus on local media channels. Reach out to local journalists from print or online papers, radio stations, school bulletins, and free magazines to explore the possibility of featuring the Living Labs. Clearly convey the project's key messages and why consumers should participate, linking it to current or local events. Consider offering interviews with enthusiastic participants who can serve as spokespersons for the project.

4. Snowballing

Leverage connections with engaged consumers to expand your participant search. Encourage these active participants to invite their networks, including friends, family, and communities, to participate in the study. Engaged consumers can serve as effective multipliers, particularly when reaching out to vulnerable groups or minorities.

3.3 Examples

In order to help you get started, this PRES includes some templates and examples of communication materials that you can draw inspiration from and use as a guideline.

Table 3. Overview of examples of communication materials.

An overview of these example exhibits can be found in **Table 3** below.

Tool	Living Lab format	Motivations used
Poster (Appendix 1)	Conventional exchange & interaction at the point of sale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product development • Desire for change • Sense of community
Flyer (Appendix 2)	Conventional exchange & interaction at the point of sale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The topic of alternative proteins is close to people's interest and values • Desire for change • Sense of community
Social Media Post (Appendix 3)	Conventional exchange & interaction at the point of sale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The topic of alternative proteins is close to people's interest and values • Curiosity and learning
Recruitment email (Appendix 4)	Conventional exchange	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The topic of alternative proteins is close to people's interest and values • Sense of community • Social cohesion/networking • Desire for change

4.

Logi- stics

Now, before you're ready to start developing your recruitment materials and approach potential participants and multipliers, it is important to think of the logistic details. In order to organise the different Living Labs formats successfully, we should carefully consider the location and accessibility, as well as the timing and duration. After all, these factors can make or break the success of your Living Labs!

4.1 Location & accessibility

The exact location of the Living Labs is quite important for their success. Within this project, the location of Living Labs will vary depending on the format and types of the Living Labs and can be best assessed by each local lab implementer. Hence, we will not specify the location directly. Nonetheless, this paragraph outlines why location and accessibility are of vital importance and highlights some guidelines and tips for good and accessible living lab locations.

4.1.1 Why are location and accessibility important?

Choosing the right location for the Living Labs is something that should not be taken lightly. **Familiar or comfortable** environments, such as community centres or local libraries, can put participants at ease. When participants feel comfortable, they are more likely to express themselves openly and honestly, leading to richer data. Additionally, for research formats involving observation, such as studying interactions at the point of sale, accessible locations allow researchers to **observe natural behaviours** without causing disruptions. Proximity to where consumers typically make purchasing decisions provides valuable insights into real-world scenarios.

When looking at accessibility, **participant convenience** is important because easy accessibility encourages participation. When participants find the research location convenient to reach, they are more likely to engage

actively, leading to a more diverse and representative sample. Moreover, accessible locations ensure that a **diverse range of participants** can attend. This diversity is essential for qualitative research, as it provides a broader perspective on consumer behaviours and attitudes. It helps in avoiding biases that may arise from a limited or homogeneous participant pool. Making sure that locations are easily accessible also minimizes the barriers for participants, reducing the likelihood of dropouts or no-shows and **increasing participant retention**. When participants face difficulties in reaching the research location, they may lose interest or find it inconvenient, leading to a higher dropout rate. Furthermore, ensuring accessibility also means considering the needs of participants with disabilities. Wheelchair ramps, elevators, and other accommodations make the research **inclusive**, allowing people with diverse abilities to participate fully. Moreover, choosing reputable and easily accessible venues enhances the **credibility of the research**. Participants are more likely to trust and engage with research conducted in professional and accessible settings. All in all, choosing accessible locations makes it not only easier to attract and retain a broad group of participants, but also makes your own life as a lab implementer easier. Clear directions, public transportation options, and ample parking facilities make the research process **smoother and more efficient**.

Identifying potential barriers to participation of your different target groups can prove very useful. For example: A person feels uncertain about being welcome in a church hall due to a different religion. Your possible solution: change the location to a more inclusive venue. Another example: A person is deaf and relies on sign language interpretation. Possible solution: provide an interpreter. It can be helpful to address these concerns in advance and provide consumers with accessibility details (e.g. mentioning that the venue has no stairs, and outlining the available support). This approach alleviates the burden on individuals and demonstrates a commitment to making the Living Labs as accessible as possible.

4.1.2 Guidelines for choosing the right location

How to choose the right location for each living lab format and make them as accessible as possible?

Table 4a. Guidelines for choosing the right Living Labs location.

Living lab format	Potential locations	Tips for ensuring accessibility
<p>Conventional exchange</p>	<p>Community centres These provide a neutral and familiar environment for participants, encouraging open discussion.</p> <p>University campuses Accessible to diverse groups and often equipped with suitable spaces for discussions.</p> <p>Local libraries Quiet and comfortable spaces that can accommodate group discussions and activities.</p> <p>Non-traditional workspace studios Better for new experiences and fostering creativity and innovation.</p> <p>Research facilities Collaborate with research institutions or labs equipped with facilities for product testing and feedback sessions.</p>	<p>Public transportation Choose locations near bus stops or train stations to ensure easy access for participants who rely on public transport.</p> <p>Wheelchair accessibility Ensure the venue is wheelchair-friendly with ramps and elevators.</p> <p>Parking facilities If participants are likely to drive, provide information about nearby parking lots or spaces.</p> <p>Clear directions Provide clear instructions and maps for participants to easily find the venue.</p> <p>Remote participation Consider offering virtual participation options for participants who cannot attend in person due to distance or other constraints.</p> <p>Size Should be large enough to host approximately 30–40 participants with the possibility of working in smaller groups.</p>

Table 4 below provides a good guideline. Of course, besides the guidelines mentioned below, it goes without saying that the first and foremost requirements for each location are (1) that they are equipped with the proper **logistics** (to conduct a consumer engagement activity and/or presenting food products including here facilities to store, tools to taste/provide feedback in a proper way, legal permissions etc. (if necessary), (2) that they are **financially viable** options in terms of available project resources and (3) that **permission** of and **collaboration** with the location are ensured to allow for a seamless process.

Table 4b. Guidelines for choosing the right Living Labs location.

Living lab format	Potential locations	Tips for ensuring accessibility
<p>Interaction at the point of sale</p>	<p>Supermarkets In grocery stores, Living Labs participants can be observed in real shopping scenarios, providing valuable insights into their natural behaviour, and purchasing decisions.</p> <p>Farmers’ markets Offers a vibrant and authentic setting for observing consumer behaviour related to fresh produce.</p> <p>Cafes or restaurants Informal settings can promote relaxed conversations, making participants feel at ease.</p> <p>University / school / business canteens Ideal for exploring behaviours in an education / work setting.</p>	<p>Proximity to residential areas Choose locations near (a diverse range of) residential neighbourhoods to ensure convenience for participants.</p> <p>Conventional / mainstream points of sale Aim to work with conventional / mainstream points of sale rather than specialty food stores (e.g. organic shops) in order to reach the ‘mainstream consumer’ and not bias towards the ‘green consumer’.</p> <p>Accessible food environments Ensure that the chosen food environment is accessible. E.g. for a store: make sure it has clear aisles, making it easy for participants, including those with disabilities, to navigate.</p>

The AFTER – how to keep participants informed?

Within the context of the Living Labs, it is not necessary to work with returning participants. However, it is still important to remain in contact with participants in the aftermath of the Living Labs in order to provide them with any important updates and outcomes of the project. Think, for instance, of contacting participants to thank them for their participation, to let them know when the results of the Living Labs can be expected, and eventually, send them an update when the results are in. This helps ensure that participants continue to feel part of the community and can see the impact of their contributions.

Retaining contact can be done, for instance, through:

- **A newsletter:** (regular) newsletters shared through a mailing list. Keep in mind that the mailing list should be updated as the Living Labs progress to include new participants.
- **Online forums:** Setting up a discussion forum (such as Slack) can be a good option, as it offers opportunities for a two-way conversation, with participants able to engage with Living Lab organisers as well as with each other. Creating a Facebook group is also an option, although it requires more regular updates and may not be as engaging.

4.2 Timing & duration

Carefully considering the timing and duration of the living labs is crucial for multiple reasons. First and foremost, **participant availability** is vital to the success of the Living Labs, so choosing convenient timings increases the likelihood of participants being available and willing to participate. It allows a broader range of people to join, ensuring diverse perspectives and experiences in the study.

This means, of course, that you should **accommodate different schedules** when deciding on the living lab timings. Participants might have work, family, or other commitments. Flexible timing, such as evenings or weekends, accommodates different schedules, making it easier for a variety of individuals to participate.

With regards to the duration of the living labs, one thing that you absolutely want is to **prevent participant fatigue**. Planning appropriate durations can help in achieving this. Lengthy or inconvenient sessions can lead to reduced engagement, lack of focus, and lower-quality responses. Optimal duration ensures participants remain attentive and provide meaningful insights throughout the session. Moreover, incorporating **enough breaks** helps prevent reduced participant focus and engagement. Planning breaks within the session allows participants to refresh, ensuring their active involvement and the quality of their contributions.

Also, it is important to take into account **participant comfort**: for instance, be sure to pay attention to comfortable seating arrangements and appropriate room temperature to foster a positive participant experience.

When looking at the point-of-sale living labs specifically, it is important that you manage to observe participants' **natural behaviour**. Therefore, the timing of these Living Labs should align with the natural behaviour patterns of the participants. For instance, studying shopping behaviours during typical shopping hours provides more authentic insights than conducting sessions at unusual times.

5.

Summary

This PRES serves to help you understand how to maximize citizen participation in the Living Labs, thereby serving as a blueprint, not just for recruiting participants, but for creating a tapestry of diverse perspectives and motivations. It centres on fostering inclusivity and understanding that genuine insights stem from embracing a broad spectrum of experiences.

The first part of this PRES focuses on the WHO

and highlights the importance of a diverse and inclusive sample as well as strategies to increase diversity and inclusion. Acknowledging the importance of diversity, the strategy aims to compose a participant sample mirroring the mosaic of society, seeking a harmonious blend of ages, genders, cultures, abilities, and backgrounds. Moreover, this chapter outlines the various reasons why consumers might be interested to join the Living Labs (motivation), and how to tap into these reasons (incentives) in order to aid the recruitment process. Lastly, this section of the report acknowledges the influential role of multipliers and explains how these connectors can best be used to your advantage. Leveraging these initial informants is essential to expand participant recruitment through their diverse networks and communities.

The second part of the PRES focuses on the HOW

and gives a good insight into how to develop effective recruitment messages and which tools are most suited for reaching different recruitment objectives. With regards to messaging, the importance of crafting simple, clear, positive, relatable, relevant, and attractive messages is explained. In terms of tools, the report gives a thorough overview of different online and offline recruitment tools and their pros and cons. This part of the report concludes by practical examples and templates for you to get started with crafting your own recruitment materials.

To close off the circle, this PRES elaborates on the importance of the location, accessibility, timing and duration of the Living Labs, and multiple tips are given for getting those logistic aspects of the Living Labs right.

All in all, this PRES outlines a comprehensive strategy with practical steps to foster inclusivity, engage diverse participants, and enhance the overall research quality by accommodating different motivations and demographics. It emphasizes the significance of a welcoming environment, appropriate messaging, and convenient logistics to ensure fruitful and diverse participant engagement in the Living Labs.

6.

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HELLO CHANGEMAKER, *We need you!*

Want to **co-develop** new **alternative protein products**, give your opinion and be part of an **international research project**? Then we are looking for you!

 20 MARCH 2024
123 ANYWHERE
ST.ANY CITY, ST 12345

 FOR MORE INFORMATION AND APPLICATIONS, VISIT WWW.LIVINGLABS.EU

Like a **PRO**

 Funded by the European Union

Appendix 2: Flyer

St Albans community

Like a **PRO**

Funded by
the European Union

We need you!

We are looking for research participants for our Living Labs, a European research project focusing on alternative protein foods.

Why Join Us?

- Become part of a **community across borders**
- Help **design solutions** to increase alternative protein food intake
- Contribute to better **health and sustainability** across Europe

20-28
March 2024

Interested to
participate or looking
for more information?

- Email us at hello@livinglabs.eu
- Or visit our website www.livinglabs.eu

Appendix 3: Social media post

LET'S TASTE NEW *Proteins*

**WE
NEED
YOU!**

www.livinglabs.eu

INSTAGRAM CAPTION:

Looking to spice up your shopping routine? 🛒 Come taste, test and talk about the proteins of the future with us on March 24-28 at [supermarket name and location]!

Find us at the entrance everyday between 09.00-19.00. Will we see you there? 🤖

#livinglabs #likeapro #alternativeproteins
#proteinsofthefuture #fundedbytheeuropeanunion

Appendix 4: Recruitment email

EXAMPLE EMAIL RECRUITMENT

Type of Living Lab: conventional exchange

Motivations used: *sense of community*, *social cohesion/networking*, *alternative proteins close to people's interest and values*, *desire for change*

Sender: municipality (multiplier)

Subject: Join our community in shaping the future of food!

Dear [name],

Are you passionate about shaping a healthier, more sustainable future for our community and beyond? We invite you to be a pivotal part of an incredible initiative that is redefining the way we view and consume food! As a valued member of our municipality, your voice matters. That's why we're excited to invite you to participate in our Living Labs.

What are Living Labs?

Living Labs are special places where real-life situations meet experiments. The topic? Alternative protein sources! Think of friendly workshops where people, just like you, come together to try out new ideas and solutions in the real world. In these Living Labs, we explore fresh ways to make things better, like giving feedback on the taste and texture of different alternative protein foods, evaluating packaging of new alternative protein products, or discussing the barriers and motivations for eating more alternative proteins. It's a bit like an adventure where everyone's ideas help make positive changes happen!

Join a thriving community

This groundbreaking research isn't just local – it's part of an extensive project, subsidized by the European Union and spanning across 11 pilot countries, uniting diverse communities to drive positive change. By participating, you'll become part of a dynamic community across borders. You'll have a unique opportunity to engage with a diverse group of participants from various regions, exchanging ideas, values, and experiences. Together, we'll have vibrant discussions that shape the future of food!

Your voice matters

Your perspectives on health, sustainability, and animal welfare regarding alternative proteins hold tremendous value. Your active participation means more than just sharing opinions – it's about making a tangible impact. We're committed to genuinely listening to your insights, ensuring your voice contributes to real change. Together, we'll pave the way for a more sustainable and healthier future for all.

Practical information

When? Wednesday March 20, 2024
What time? 6-7PM (Living Labs), 7-8PM (opportunity for networking over a nice drink)
Where? Horizon road 11, 1234 AB, Labcity
How? Click [link] to sign up or find out more.

We believe that together, we can create a profound impact on our community's well-being and contribute to a brighter, sustainable future for generations to come.

Don't miss this chance to be part of something transformative! Join us in shaping the future of food.

Ready to make a difference? Click [link] to sign up or find out more.

Thank you for being an integral part of our community's journey towards a better, healthier tomorrow.

Warm regards,
 [Name]
 [Position]
 [Contact Information]

P.S. Your participation matters! Don't miss the opportunity to shape the future of food in our community – sign up now!

Participant Recruitment and Engagement Strategy

**LIKE-A-PRO's Food Environment
Citizen Innovation Living Labs**

Building a better world
through alternative sources
of protein

like-a-pro.eu

Funded by
the European Union